

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP3

NA2 - Dissemination, Communication, and Collaboration

Deliverable D3.1

D-NA2.1 Project Marketing and Strategic Dissemination and Communication Plan

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List of Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
CO	Coordinator
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CP	Collaboration Platform
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
JRA	Joint Research Activities
LoS	Letter of Support
NA	Networking Activities
RI	Research Infrastructure
TA	Trans-national Access
VA	Virtual Access
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document provides a plan for the communication and dissemination of the ERIGrid 2.0 project activities and cooperation with project stakeholders. As a project with significant focus on the audience involvement due to its Research Infrastructure (RI) access opportunities, educational and knowledge transfer activities, ERIGrid 2.0 must ensure engagement with certain target groups. Among these major target groups are: industry professionals, researchers and academics, relevant research initiatives and networks, Master and PhD students. The strategic plan makes clear the added value delivered by ERIGrid 2.0 to each of these groups. Correspondingly, the most appropriate channels for the promotion and dissemination are identified in each case.

Furthermore, this plan details the aspect of communication with the already established stakeholders and the potential new ones. It provides guidelines to the project partners regarding the dissemination and stakeholder engagement. Included in this strategic plan is also an overview of the relevant reports and milestones to be delivered.

Upon providing the strategy for communication, dissemination and collaboration, the document moves on to the visual identity and elaborates the project marketing materials and tools used for project promotion. Adopting consistent visual identity in the project contributes to successful promotion. The marketing materials provided are: press releases, flyer, poster, and the presentation template. The tools and platforms used in the project and elaborated in this document are: website, newsletter, and social media.

In the conclusion of the document it is emphasised that the focus of the strategic communication plan is the engagement with the target audience in order to reach the project objectives. Therefore, the consortium shall invest significant joint effort in communication, dissemination and collaboration.

However, facing the impacts of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) as an unprecedented global crisis, the consortium must respond accordingly to the changed situation. We are all experiencing a disruption of our routines of daily life and work, partly general travel bans have been issued by our employers. Thus, in an approach of shared responsibility and solidarity, wishing that all partners and stakeholders of the project can stay safe, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium wants to stay productive in the sense of reaching the project targets and fulfilling the tasks according to the time schedule. Therefore, we will have to adopt alternative communication patterns and channels to cope with the new situation. Most of the present and upcoming meetings and other activities like trainings will be organised on a virtual basis, and research collaboration will be strengthened via existing platforms like MS Teams, GoToWebinar, ResearchGate, etc. Since the ERIGrid 2.0 partners are familiar with using electronic collaboration tools and holding remote presentations, it can be expected that the activities of the project will proceed as planned.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

Communication and dissemination are crucial activities for the transmission of project activities and outcomes to the target audiences.

This document presents materials and channels that form the marketing set of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It also provides information on how these materials are planned to be used depending on the specific purpose, target group and occasion. These materials and, where applicable, guidelines are developed to ensure consistent visual identity to the project in the process of promotion and establishing collaboration.

Therefore, this document gives a comprehensive overview of both the strategy and the tools that the project will utilise in its communication, dissemination and collaboration with other actors.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows. Section 1 provides an overview of the document's purpose, scope and structure. Section 2 elaborates the plan for establishing and maintaining communication activities, with more detail on the target groups, the approaches and the tools that the consortium will utilise. The promotion and marketing materials are detailed in Section 3. Finally, conclusions are provided in Section 4. The Appendix A: Press Releases, Appendix B: Flyer, Appendix C: Poster, Appendix D: Rollup and Appendix E: Presentation Template demonstrate the described materials.

2 Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan

Noteworthy regarding the overall communication strategy is that thanks to its predecessor ERI-Grid 2.0 can build on all the past experience and make direct use of the available best practices. This strategy allows, on one hand, efficient and targeted exploitation of the ERIGrid 2.0 outcomes, and, on the other hand, it ensures efficient dissemination of the current project right from its start. Specific examples are given correspondingly in the following sections.

2.1 Objectives

The goals of the ERIGrid 2.0 communication, dissemination and collaboration activities are in line with the project's overarching mission to support smart grid and smart energy systems research, technology development, validation and roll-out. According to the Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019), they are as follows:

- Creating of a strong project image and establishing the right dissemination and communications tools,
- Establishing collaboration with other European and international and national projects, initiatives and networks,
- Dissemination and communication of non-confidential scientific results of the Networking Activities (NA) and Joint Research Activities (JRA) to the scientific community and industry as well as to other relevant stakeholder groups (incl. policy makers) during the project execution, following the open access policy of Horizon 2020 (H2020), and
- Broad dissemination of the RI access opportunities to the potential users from research, academia and industry.

Considering these objectives as well as the project goal to foster system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development, it is critical to provide a transfer of project results to the target audience and to engage them in the activities of the project.

2.2 Target Groups and Specific Measures, Channels

The communication with the target audience and the dissemination of the project value to them is of particularly high importance to ERIGrid 2.0 as a project providing RI access, outstanding knowledge transfer and educational opportunities to external users. It is therefore crucial to establish and maintain communication, dissemination and collaboration in such a way that they reach the end users in the most efficient and engaging way.

Identifying target audiences in a more specific manner is critical for successful project communication and dissemination. Herewith we refer to the target group as a single stakeholder or a stakeholder group.

Based on the objectives listed in Section 2.1, ERIGrid 2.0 identified the following target audiences, all involved in the smart grid and smart energy systems research, testing and validation domains. To each of these target groups ERIGrid 2.0 strives to provide a corresponding value, i.e., as an outcome of JRAs or NAs, as a Trans-national Access (TA) or Virtual Access (VA) opportunity, etc. These target groups are not to be considered strictly separate as they can

overlap. Therefore, the focus of this overview is on the aspects and nuances of the project communication in each case rather than on setting target audiences apart.

2.2.1 Industry

Attracting industry's attention is of particular importance to the project as it strives to secure early adoption of the developed outcomes. Furthermore, communication with this target group and their feedback should support the project in remaining relevant with its ambitions. Obtaining a significant number of industry-related user projects (at least 25% of all user projects) is also one of the objectives for TA/VA activities (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019). Therefore, ERIGrid 2.0 aims to bridge the collaboration and knowledge exchange between academia and industry. The goal of the communication with this target group is to establish a dialogue, continuously engage with them and motivate them to interact with the project.

Strong support in this activity is expected from the Advisory Board (AB), in particular regarding the feedback, recommendations for direction, and strategy for attracting industry TA project proposals and usage of VA services. Within the Task NA1.1 *Advisory Board and Links with Industrial User Groups / Associations*, communication with AB members will take place through meetings at least once a year and through individual interactions.

A number of industry representatives are also among the 70 stakeholders who had provided Letter of Support (LoS) during the planning phase of the project. As they are already familiar with ERIGrid 2.0 objectives and activities, the goal of the communication with them is to maintain strong contact and to involve them in the project activities through dedicated stakeholder workshops or other industry events, and feedback collection. This effort is realised systematically on the project level by NA1 and NA2. However, each of the partners is responsible for maintaining individual contact with specific stakeholders they had attracted to provide LoS. This may include following up on certain individual invitations to project events and requests to provide feedback to project activities. Based on the ERIGrid experience, this approach can guarantee consistent and effective interaction with the established stakeholders.

Having this group of industry representatives among the project stakeholders is considered a starting point to build on and to expand the industry audience even more throughout the project. This action is to be realised through promotion at dedicated project events, industry events attended by project partners, and the project involvement in relevant industry-represented networks (CIRED, CIGRE, etc.). This is the focus of Task NA 1.2 *Networking and Cooperation with Industry*. A detailed overview of industry engagement will be reported in two project reports: D-NA1.4a and D-NA1.4b 'Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours', due in M24 and M48 correspondingly.

Within the frame of Task NA1.3 *Knowledge Transfer to (Industrial) Stakeholder Groups*, exploitable results from JRA will be published in form of factsheets, based on the needs of the industrial community.

Important for systematic and broad dissemination to the industrial community is each of the partners' individual effort in networking and project promotion to this target group. This action can significantly multiply the project outreach, especially considering the broad networks of industry partners in the consortium, as shown by the experience in ERIGrid.

2.2.2 Research and Academia

Being a research project itself and having a significant share of research institutions in the consortium, ERIGrid 2.0 already has strong connections with research and academia. Also among the stakeholders who had submitted letters of support are representatives from this target group. Nevertheless, as with all other groups, the consortium aims to expand the outreach in this direction.

JRA outcomes are of interest to this target group and their further exploitation in research and academic settings. ERIGrid 2.0 will therefore ensure that the project results are disseminated to major stakeholders in this group through general project promotion, but also through participation at scientific events, dedicated ERIGrid 2.0 workshops and educational activities in NA3, in particular in Task NA3.1 *Organisation of Workshops, Summer Schools, and Training Courses*. However due to the COVID-19 crisis at the time of this deliverable, the virtual character of events shall prevail until further notice.

ERIGrid 2.0 offer of TA/VA access is also of high interest to this target audience. The promotion of the RI access therefore strongly targets research and academia. This is realised, among other measures, through participation in scientific events and direct outreach via partners' individual channels and networks. With a share of research and academia institutions represented in the consortium, partners will contribute to reaching this target group through their contact networks. DERlab in particular, as an association of over 30 research centres in Europe and the US and as the NA2 leader, will utilise its network to broaden project exposure.

2.2.3 Projects, Networks, Initiatives

Building on the collaboration experience in the predecessor project, ERIGrid 2.0 will continue cooperating with and establish new connections with relevant H2020 research consortia, research clusters, local or national authorities, standardisation bodies, coordination groups and technical committees. This collaboration will be done by all partners on both national and international levels. The collaboration between ERIGrid 2.0 and other initiatives will be beneficial for both sides in terms of knowledge exchange and improving the integrated RI services. Besides gaining valuable insight from these stakeholders, the goal of the ERIGrid 2.0 interaction with this target group is to foster early exploitation of project outcomes.

Examples of suitable initiatives for that purpose are IEEE P2004 Working Group (WG) on 'Recommended Practice for Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) Simulation Based Testing of Electric Power Apparatus and Controls', as well as IEC, CEN, CENELEC, and other IEEE communities. Among relevant projects are, for example, United-Grid, CloudGrid and LarGo!, meanwhile among relevant initiatives ERA-NET Smart Energy Systems, EERA alliance and BRIDGE are to be considered. Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 aims to establish cooperation with IEA ISGAN, ISGAN Annex 5 SIRFN, IEEE Task Force on 'Real-Time Simulation of Power and Energy Systems'. All the mentioned initiatives have already collaborated with ERIGrid in the past, and the connections are therefore still present. Maintenance of this contact and collaboration, as well as establishment of new areas of collaboration, are mainly done through ERIGrid 2.0 partners represented in other projects' consortia. The transfer of ideas is to take place continuously through direct exchange of information, joint workshops, webinars and other activities.

In detail the cooperation with projects and initiatives will be reported in the project reports: D-NA2.2a, D-NA2.2b, and D-NA2.2c 'Progress Report of Project Networking and Collaboration Activities', due in M12, M30 and M48 correspondingly. This activity is supported by tasks

NA1.3 *Knowledge Transfer to (Industrial) Stakeholder Groups*, NA1.5 *Pre-normative Standardisation Activities* and NA2.2 *Networking, Cooperation and Knowledge Exchange*, also in close collaboration with Task NA1.2 *Networking and Cooperation with Industry*.

2.2.4 Master and PhD Students

A very relevant target group for the ERIGrid 2.0 objectives are Master and PhD students of electrical engineering with focus on system integration and testing. This group will gain significant benefit from ERIGrid 2.0 research outcomes and, most importantly, educational activities and RI access opportunities. Therefore, the dissemination to this target group focuses on promotion of ERIGrid 2.0 educational events organised within NA3 and the TA/VA opportunities. Besides general promotion performed by DERlab as NA2 leader, academic and research lecturing partners should disseminate this relevant information to their students.

2.3 Activities Addressing All Target Groups

Elaborated below are continuous activities for communication, dissemination and collaboration, reaching all the target groups throughout the project.

Led by DERlab, dissemination and cooperation with stakeholders is a joint effort of the entire consortium. Each project partner ensures consistent communication of project activities and dissemination of project results through their own networks and channels, both on the national and international levels.

2.3.1 General Promotion and Marketing

To reach all target audiences and disseminate project results to them, ERIGrid 2.0 makes use of the online channels and marketing materials detailed in Section 3.

2.3.2 Scientific Dissemination

Project contribution to relevant power engineering conferences and journal articles, such as IEEE conferences and journals, CIGRE, CIGRE, CIGRE, CIGRE, CIGRE, etc., ensures successful dissemination of project results to the target audiences. This kind of exposure is effort-consuming yet crucial for ERIGrid 2.0 visibility to the scientific community. The tentative list of relevant conferences and peer-reviewed journals can be found in Table 1, with consideration of possible rescheduling or change to virtual events due to the current COVID-19 crisis.

As indicated in the GA, at least 30 scientific papers or reports are to be produced in the project. All produced publications and presentations will be published as gold open access or at least will be uploaded to the project website as green open access.

The concluding and summarising activity regarding scientific dissemination will be the ERIGrid 2.0 'European White Book on Smart Energy Systems Integration and Testing', due in M54. This publication will consolidate results from JRAs, NAs, and user projects in order to support the further development and innovation in the domain of power and energy systems. This major publication of the project will be disseminated to all project target groups.

Table 1: Relevant scientific events, non-exhaustive list.

Title	Date, Location
The 12 th Annual European Power Strategy & Systems Summit	30 Nov. - 2 Dec. 2020, Prague (CZ)
10 th IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conf.	23-27 Nov. 2020, Perth (AU)
IREC (9 th International Conference, Integration of Renewable & Distributed Energy Resources)	3-5 Feb. 2021, Adelaide (AU)
CIREC Conference and Exhibition	21-24 June 2021, Geneva (CH)
CIGRE Technical Exhibition	21-25 Aug. 2021, Paris (FR)

Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 will gain large-scale exposure through the DERlab Activity Report 2023-2024. Through subsequent extensive online and offline dissemination of this report, ERIGrid 2.0 will reach key stakeholders from research, academia, industry, policy in the field of smart grids and Distributed Energy Resources (DER).

2.3.3 Promotion of Research Infrastructure Access

A significant part of the overall project promotion effort is to be invested in the promotion of the RI access. For this objective, all of the channels are to be utilised, with particular focus on partners' individual networking. Based on the ERIGrid experience, the promotion through individual partners' networking is the most effective and should be focused further on in ERIGrid 2.0. The basis for such face-to-face promotion is partners' own activities and events, with the help of developed marketing materials in Section 3. Additionally, ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholder workshops and educational events are suitable for such activity.

In addition to partners' promotion, all of the other promotion tools and channels are of course utilised as well, such as announcements through the project website, social media, and newsletters. In particular and considering the already established following, project social media appear to be an effective channel for consistent promotion of the RI access, with frequent posts highlighting each of the available RIs.

2.3.4 Workshop Organisation

Coordinated by Task NA2.4 *Event Organisation* in close collaboration with NA1 and NA3 leaders, at least three workshops are foreseen in the project in order to review the project progress, gather stakeholders' feedback and possibly align the course. These events will also facilitate transfer of project results and thus foster exploitation.

The consortium aims to couple these workshops to relevant scientific conferences in order to increase project exposure, reach a high number of attendees and establish new liaisons. Preliminary examples of such conferences are given in Table 1. Noteworthy here again is that the consortium has to remain flexible in the light of COVID-19 and might consider organising workshops as virtual events until the situation improves.

Generally, ERIGrid 2.0's presence at national and international events is a key way to obtain feedback on the project activities and results from stakeholders. In cases of preparation for ERIGrid 2.0 events, each partner, additionally to the NA2 project promotion, utilises their own corporate, business channels and networks with the aim to attract relevant audience.

2.4 Schedule

The schedule of major achievements in communication, dissemination and cooperation is determined by the schedules of corresponding deliverables and milestones in Work Package (WP)3-NA2 and WP2-NA1 as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Relevant milestones and deliverables.

Number	Title	Lead	Due Date
MS4	M-NA2.1 First TA Call Launched ^a	DERlab	M1
MS5	M-NA2.2 Marketing Materials Available and Distributed	DERlab	M4
D3.1	D-NA2.1 Project Marketing and Strategic Dissemination and Communication Plan	DERlab	M4
D3.2	D-NA2.2a Progress Report of Project Networking and Collaboration Activities	DERlab	M12
D3.5	D-NA2.3a Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls	DERlab	M24
D2.7	D-NA1.4a Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours	HEDNO	M24
D3.3	D-NA2.2b Progress Report of Project Networking and Collaboration Activities	DERlab	M30
D3.6	D-NA2.3b Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls	DERlab	M37
D3.4	D-NA2.2c Progress Report of Project Networking and Collaboration Activities	DERlab	M48
D2.8	D-NA1.4b Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours	HEDNO	M48
D3.7	D-NA2.3c Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls	DERlab	M51
D3.8	D-NA2.4 European White Book on Smart Energy Systems Integration and Testing	DERlab	M54
MS2	M-MGT.2 M-MGT.2 Final Project Meeting/Closing Event	AIT	M54
MS6	M-NA2.3 High Quality Workshops Organized	DERlab	M54

^aPostponed until further notice, due to the COVID-19 situation.

3 Project Marketing

In order to communicate project activities in a consistent and coherent way, ERIGrid 2.0 developed a set of marketing materials and templates according to the project visual identity. This consistent image will support recognition of the project by the target audience and thus facilitate efficient promotion.

In order to indicate the link with the past ERIGrid project and to help stay in touch with its audience, ERIGrid 2.0 significantly bases its visual identity, marketing and dissemination on the practices from the predecessor project. This approach supports efficient exploitation of ERIGrid 2.0 outcomes by making clear the connection between the two projects to the external community and by taking advantage of the tried and tested practices and tools.

Elaborated below are the materials, templates, tools, and channels used for marketing in ERIGrid 2.0, both for project-internal and external communication, designed and maintained by DERlab as NA2 leader in cooperation with AIT as the Coordinator (CO). All printed marketing materials comply with the general project visual identity and include a reference to the received funding from the EU's H2020 programme and the grant agreement number.

Besides designing the materials, DERlab as the NA2 leader also takes care of printing an initial batch of project flyers and distributing them to the partners. After partners run out of the printed copies, they can reprint them locally using the design files provided by DERlab.

3.1 Logo

The ERIGrid 2.0 logo (Figure 1) is based on the logo of the ERIGrid project, with a single change presenting the name change of the project.

Figure 1: ERIGrid 2.0 logo.

The project logo should appear on all documents related to ERIGrid 2.0. Any material or document (co-)funded with the project budget must have an explicit reference to it and, if possible, include the ERIGrid 2.0 logo.

3.2 Website

In order to present the project to the general public, ERIGrid 2.0 utilises its website, available at <https://erigrad2.eu>. It serves as the main information platform about the project, its goals, activities and outcomes. Through the website, the consortium aims to provide all public materials and publications from within the project easily accessible for the public. At the time of writing, the website structure consists of seven main pages (Figure 2):

- *Home*: The page highlights the current status of the TA/VA programme, includes an embedded Twitter feed of the project and recent news.
- *About*: The page presents basic facts about the project and the consortium.

- **News:** The page contains announcements of ERIGrid 2.0 activities, events, outcomes, etc.
- **Lab Access:** The page contains all information necessary for potential users regarding the TA/VA.
- **Resources:** The page presents an overview of all public materials, publications and marketing materials produced by the project. This page is planned to be linked to the list of publications, tools, software, etc. in the [ERIGrid 2.0 Zenodo Community](#).
- **Contacts:** The page provides contact details of the CO, as well as a contact form.
- **ERIGrid-1:** The section is linked to the website of the predecessor project ERIGrid for further information and to support dissemination of ERIGrid.

Further additions and modifications to the website are of course foreseen as the project matures. The website is maintained by DERlab and AIT.

Figure 2: ERIGrid 2.0 website (home page).

3.3 Newsletters

Quarterly newsletters issued by the project provide a digest of recent project news and extraordinary announcements. As foreseen in the GA, at least 16 newsletters will be released in the duration of the project. All of the newsletter issues will be listed and linked on the *Resources* page on the website. The subscription to the newsletter is open and available through the website.

In order to maintain the communication established with the newsletter audience during the predecessor project, ERIGrid 2.0 will build on the already available list of newsletter subscribers. This will enable the audience to get a clear understanding of the topics they are still interested

in within the frame of the new project. The distribution will be done through the Mailchimp platform as was done previously in ERIGrid. At the time of writing, the list of newsletter subscribers counts 386 persons and is growing almost daily.

3.4 Social Networks

In order to actively and regularly engage with the target audiences and disseminate project outcomes, ERIGrid 2.0 utilises a number of social media channels and similar platforms:

- *LinkedIn*¹ is used by ERIGrid 2.0 for highlighting ongoing announcements and interacting with stakeholders. Having built up a dedicated audience during ERIGrid, the project currently has 610 followers. Maintenance (at least one post per week) is done through NA2 leader DERlab and CO AIT.
- *Twitter*² is used by ERIGrid 2.0 for short updates from within the project and also disseminating other stakeholders' announcements. The project currently has 282 followers on Twitter. Maintenance (at least one update per week) is done through NA2 leader DERlab and CO AIT.
- *YouTube*³ is used by ERIGrid 2.0 primarily to provide video recordings of the project webinars, as was done in the predecessor project. The YouTube channel currently has 43 subscribers. Maintenance (upon the availability of video recordings) is done through NA2 leader DERlab and CO AIT.
- *ResearchGate*⁴, as a popular platform for scientific publications, is used by ERIGrid 2.0 to increase the outreach for wider scientific dissemination. Upload of publications is performed by the corresponding partners, meanwhile the control and maintenance is done through CO AIT.
- *GitHub*⁵, as a combination of a social network and a repository, is used by ERIGrid 2.0 to publicly provide its developments, tools, software, etc. to the wide audience of the platform. Upload of publications is performed by the corresponding partners, meanwhile the control and maintenance is done through CO AIT.
- *Zenodo*⁶, is used by ERIGrid 2.0 as a platform for publishing all project-related materials, including publications, presentations, webinars, tools, etc. Upload of materials is performed by the corresponding partners, meanwhile the control and maintenance is done through CO AIT.

3.5 Press Release

At the start of the project CO AIT produced a press release with focus on their SmartEST Laboratory in order to inform the public about project activities. This press release is available in English and German languages. Based on that press release, DERlab prepared a general project press release to provide an overview about the main goals and objectives (see Appendix

¹<https://www.linkedin.com/company/erigrd-project>

²<https://twitter.com/ERIGrid>

³<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCed120ku-VIMIZOXu092gXQ/featured>

⁴<https://www.researchgate.net/project/European-Research-Infrastructure-supporting-Smart-Grid-and-Smart-Energy-Systems-Research-Technology-Development-Validation-and-Roll-Out-Second-Edition-ERIGrid-20>

⁵<https://github.com/ERIGrid2>

⁶<https://zenodo.org/communities/erigrd2>

A: Press Releases). The press releases were provided to the project consortium for their individual distribution. Distribution through project channels is to be carried out as well.

3.6 Project Flyer

The ERIGrid 2.0 project flyer (Appendix B: Flyer) comes in the format DIN long, letter fold, which is an efficient format for getting across the basic facts and the focus of the project, both to the general public and to any specific audience. This format is also practical during physical dissemination, e.g., at conferences, workshops, lab visits, etc.

Contrary to the practice in the previous ERIGrid project, ERIGrid 2.0 took the approach to combine both the general project promotion and the TA/VA promotion in one flyer rather than in two different ones. This has been done with the practical aim to provide information about the entire project concisely in one piece of communication and thus optimise the distribution. The flyer will also be available as a download on the website.

3.7 Poster

The project poster (Appendix C: Poster) presents major information about ERIGrid 2.0 in a big format, designed for presentations at events. The design file is provided by DERlab to the project consortium to be printed and used on demand.

3.8 Rollup

The project rollup banner (Appendix D: Rollup) is a mobile promotional piece, designed for big-format information display and highlighting ERIGrid 2.0 presence at events. The design file is provided by DERlab to the project consortium to be printed and used on demand.

3.9 Technical Factsheets

As documented in the GA, after the outcomes of the JRAs become available, dedicated factsheets will be designed and transferred to the target audience in order to ensure early adoption of results. As foreseen, these factsheets will be based on the project visual identity. They will be published in the format A4, which allows for a succinct initial presentation of the outcomes.

3.10 PowerPoint Presentation Template

For various dissemination purposes throughout the project, ERIGrid 2.0 developed a presentation template (Appendix E: Presentation Template), which will be used by all partners at the occasions of presenting ERIGrid 2.0 related content.

3.11 Deliverable Template

With consideration of the general project identity, the consortium developed a deliverable report template in \LaTeX which is available at the project Collaboration Platform (CP)⁷. This template is used for all project deliverable reports. All reports with the public dissemination status will be published at the project's Zenodo Community, the project website and disseminated through other project channels.

⁷<https://teams.microsoft.com/>

4 Conclusions

The current document presents an overview of the available tools and the plan for communication, dissemination and collaboration. As presented, the already available best practices, tools, and experience from ERIGrid will be very beneficial for the promotion of ERIGrid 2.0. Nonetheless with all the advantages considered, the engagement of the target audiences is still a challenging and effort-intensive task. Therefore, all the recommendations and guidelines given in this document are to be considered by the project consortium. The detailed marketing materials should assist the consortium in this effort.

An unforeseen risk for the project management is performing communication and implementing the project goals in the current COVID-19 situation which concerns all partners and all stakeholders of the project. Nevertheless, the consortium will strive to attract users and offer alternative ways of taking part in the project. The use of electronic tools and virtual collaboration platforms has in the meantime become a common practise of the consortium, and we are thus confident to manage and overcome this issue by finding creative and innovative solutions, accelerating digitalisation and pushing innovation.

References

ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement. (2019). European Commission.

Appendix A: Press Releases

A.1 General Version

ERIGRID 2.0 ENABLES OPEN ACCESS TO SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

Vienna, 10 July 2020 - Building on the achievements of the predecessor project, ERIGRID 2.0 extends its research to the scope of the entire smart energy system and broadens the range of lab services for external users.

Led by the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, the European consortium of innovative research and development laboratories offers research infrastructure of the ERIGRID partners to young researchers and experts for developing, testing and validating modern power supply systems, the integration of renewable energies, the digitalization of the networks and intelligent energy systems. The project is based on holistic, cyber-physical validations of the energy system, which can also be carried out in virtual environments. All in all, 21 smart grid and smart energy systems laboratories and 8 facilities with virtual access will be available free-of-charge for successful applicants from all over the world to advance their own research. Access to the laboratories is granted from 2020 to 2024.

The current transformation and digitalization of the energy system while ensuring security of supply require new approaches for the conversion, storage and distribution of energy in different areas. “ERIGRID 2.0 opens the doors of Europe’s best research infrastructures for young researchers to advance the development and validation of new concepts and approaches for the integrated energy system of the future,” explains Thomas Strasser, senior scientist at the Center for Energy of the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology and coordinator of ERIGRID 2.0. “They will have free physical and virtual access to perform their research activities between April 2020 and September 2024. Another important contribution of the project is training and further education for qualified employees of laboratories and infrastructure facilities,” says Strasser.

About

- ERIGRID 2.0: European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition
- 20 partners from research, academia and industry
- 21 first-class European laboratories and 8 virtual facilities involved
- 12 European countries represented in the consortium
- Duration: 1 April 2020 – 30 September 2024
- Budget: € 10M funded by the European Commission

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement 870620

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A.2 AIT Version (English)

Press information

Vienna, June 9, 2020

ERIGrid 2.0 enables open access for research on the energy system infrastructure

The AIT SmartEST laboratory is part of ERIGrid 2.0 and offers young researchers and experts free physical and virtual access

Based on its successful predecessor project of the same name, ERIGrid 2.0 expands the research services and instruments of its infrastructures, which are now also open to external users. The Center for Energy of the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology leads the European consortium of innovative research and development laboratories that offers the ERIGrid partners' research infrastructure to young researchers and experts for developing, testing and validating modern power supply systems, the integration of renewable energies, the digitalization of the networks and intelligent energy systems. The project is based on holistic, cyber-physical validations of the energy system, which can also be carried out in virtual environments. Access is granted from 2020 to 2024.

Open access offers new opportunities for researchers and industrial experts

The current transformation and digitalization of the energy system while ensuring security of supply require new approaches for the conversion, storage and distribution of energy in different areas. "ERIGrid 2.0 opens the doors of Europe's best research infrastructures for young researchers to advance the development and validation of new concepts and approaches for the integrated energy system of the future," explains Thomas Strasser, senior scientist at the Center for Energy of the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology and coordinator of ERIGrid 2.0. "They will have free physical and virtual access to perform their research activities between April 2020 and September 2024. Another important contribution of the project is training and further education for qualified employees of laboratories and infrastructure facilities," says Strasser.

AIT SmartEST laboratory is part of ERIGrid 2.0

With the SmartEST (Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies) laboratory, AIT has a development platform for smart grid technologies and system architectures that is unique in Europe. Solutions and products from industrial partners are tested here, and AIT develops innovations which will later be transferred to the market. Electrical energy storage systems and their current and future tasks in the energy system are presently in high demand. Of particular interest for the ERIGrid 2.0 project are applications like controllers and power hardware-in-the-loop (PHIL), and the simulation of smart grid and smart energy systems scenarios (sector coupling).

About the project

ERIGrid 2.0 (European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out - Second Edition) under the direction of the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology unites 20 innovation partners from 13 European countries to create a transnational platform for the benefit of research, industry and network operators.

<https://erigid2.eu/>

A.3 AIT Version (German)

Presseinformation

Wien, 08.06.2020

ERIGrid 2.0 ermöglicht Open-Access für Forschung an der Energiesysteminfrastruktur

AIT SmartEST-Labor ist Teil von ERIGrid 2.0 und bietet jungen Forschenden und Expert*innen einen freien physischen und virtuellen Zugang

ERIGrid 2.0 öffnet und erweitert, aufbauend auf seinem gleichnamigen erfolgreichen Vorgängerprojekt, die Forschungsdienste und -instrumente seiner Infrastrukturen, die nun auch für externe Benutzer*innen geöffnet werden. Das Center for Energy des AIT Austrian Institute of Technology leitet das europäische Konsortium innovativer Forschungs- und Entwicklungslabors, das jungen Forschenden und Expert*innen die Forschungsinfrastruktur der ERIGrid-Partner für die Entwicklung, Erprobung und Validierung moderner Stromversorgungssysteme, die Integration erneuerbarer Energien, die Digitalisierung der Netze und intelligente Energiesysteme anbietet. Das Projekt basiert auf ganzheitlichen, cyber-physischen Validierungen des Energiesystems, die auch in virtuellen Umgebungen durchgeführt werden können. Der Zugang wird von 2020 bis 2024 gewährt.

Open-Access bietet neue Chancen für Forschende und Expert*innen aus der Industrie

Die aktuelle Transformation und Digitalisierung des Energiesystems bei gleichzeitiger Gewährleistung der Versorgungssicherheit erfordern neue Ansätze für die Umwandlung, Speicherung und Verteilung von Energie in verschiedenen Bereichen.

„ERIGrid 2.0 öffnet sozusagen die Türen der besten Forschungsinfrastrukturen Europas für junge Forscherinnen und Forscher, um die Entwicklung und Validierung von neuartigen Ansätzen und Konzepten für das integrierte Energiesystem der Zukunft voranzubringen“, erklärt Thomas Strasser, Privatdozent und Senior Scientist am Center for Energy des AIT Austrian Institute of Technology und Koordinator von ERIGrid 2.0. „Sie bekommen im Zeitraum von April 2020 bis September 2024 einen gebührenfreien physischen und virtuellen Zugang für ihre Forschungsaktivitäten. Ein weiterer wichtiger Beitrag des Projekts ist die Aus- und Weiterbildung, um qualifizierte Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter für Labore und Infrastruktureinrichtungen auszubilden“, so Strasser.

AIT SmartEST-Labor ist Teil von ERIGrid 2.0

Mit dem SmartEST (Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies) Labor verfügt das AIT über eine in Europa einzigartige Entwicklungsplattform für Smart Grid Technologien und Systemarchitekturen. Hier werden Lösungen und Produkte von Industriepartnern getestet, aber auch AIT-Innovationen entwickelt, die später in den Markt übergeleitet werden. Elektrische Energiespeichersysteme und deren aktuelle und zukünftige Aufgaben im Energiesystem zählen gegenwärtig zu nachgefragten Technologien. Für das Projekt ERIGrid 2.0 sind Controller und Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL)-Anwendungen und die Simulation von Smart Grid und Smart Energy Systems Szenarien (Sektorkopplung) von besonderem Interesse.

Appendix B: Flyer

FREE PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL LAB ACCESS

apply every 3 months for physical lab access

access virtual services anytime no application required

The ERIGrid 2.0 project invites all interested engineers in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and smart energy to receive free funding to access the best laboratories and services of Europe for their own experimental research. Physical lab access can be organised either on-site or remotely. Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 provides virtual access to 8 facilities and services without applications required.

USERS WILL RECEIVE:

- on-site or remote access to 21 first-class laboratories or application-free virtual access to 8 services of ERIGrid partners
- in case of physical access: funding for their complete research stay at the location of the selected laboratory, including coverage of expenses for travelling, accommodation and lab operation costs
- access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grids and energy systems components characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT / automation validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power/Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), and others
- opportunity to advance their own research and solutions
- working with the top smart grid and energy systems experts
- chance to impact EU industry
- promotion of their research through ERIGrid 2.0 channels

Find detailed descriptions of labs and services and all further details at erigid2.eu/lab-access.

CONSORTIUM COORDINATED BY **AIT** AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

CONNECTING EUROPEAN SMART GRID RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FREE ACCESS TO EUROPE'S BEST SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

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Supported by the H2020 Programme under Contract No. 870620

Based on the results from the predecessor project ERIGrid-1, ERIGrid 2.0 will expand the research services and tools of research infrastructures for validating smart energy networks with the electric power grid as the main backbone.

ABOUT

- ERIGrid 2.0: European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition
- 20 partners from research, academia and industry
- 21 first-class European labs provided to external users for free access on-site or remotely
- 8 facilities and services provided to external users for virtual access
- 13 European countries represented in the consortium
- Duration: 1 April 2020 – 30 September 2024
- Budget: € 10M funded by the European Commission

GOALS

- support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy systems approaches, concepts, and solutions in Europe taking a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach into account
- provide system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- enhance system-level validation methods
- improve and extend tools to accommodate system-level tests over multiple test infrastructures and domains
- implement and demonstrate the developed concepts, methods, and tools into the research infrastructures (RI) of the ERIGrid 2.0 partners

NETWORKING OBJECTIVES

- knowledge-exchange with other European smart grid and smart energy systems RIs
- knowledge transfer between researchers, technicians, and RI managers
- Open Access (OA) provision of achievements and reinforced collaboration with industry and energy utilities
- education of power and energy system professionals
- international collaboration and harmonization

Appendix C: Poster

Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

Supported by the H2020 Programme under Contract No. 870620

CONNECTING EUROPEAN SMART GRID RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FREE ACCESS TO EUROPE'S BEST SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

Based on the results from the predecessor project ERIGrid-1, ERIGrid 2.0 will expand the research services and tools of research infrastructures for validating smart energy networks with the electric power grid as the main backbone.

GOALS

- support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy systems approaches, concepts, and solutions in Europe taking a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach into account
- provides system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development

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- knowledge-exchange with other European smart grid and smart energy systems RIs
- knowledge transfer between researchers, technicians, and RI managers
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- international collaboration and harmonization

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- improve and extend tools to accommodate system-level tests over multiple test infrastructures and domains
- implement and demonstrate the developed concepts, methods, and tools into the research infrastructures (RI) of the ERIGrid 2.0 partners

COORDINATED BY

User and Stakeholder Needs

- Liaison with Initiatives and Associations (NA1)
- Dissemination, Communication, and Cooperation (NA2)
- Staff Exchange, Education and Training (NA3)
- Scenario and Test Case Creation (NA4)

ERIGRID 2.0 – European RI for Smart Grids, Smart Energy Systems, and Renewables Research

Sustainable, Low-Carbon Energy Policy

- 2012 Paris Agreement
- EU "Clean Energy for All Europeans" package
- EU Vision 2050

EU Energy Transition Goal: Creation of a low-carbon, secure, reliable, resilient, accessible, cost-efficient, and market-based pan-European integrated energy system

Management of Access Activities (NAS)

Trans-national and Virtual Access to ERIGRID 2.0 Research Infrastructure (NAS, TA1, TA2, VA)

- Industrial user groups / vendors
- Academic user groups
- Project consortia (European & national projects)

apply every 3 months for physical lab access

access virtual services anytime no application required

COORDINATED BY

ERIGRID 2.0 Project:
1 April 2020 - 30 September 2024
20 Partners from 13 European countries
21 first-class smart grid labs
8 virtual facilities and services

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Appendix D: Rollup

Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

CONNECTING EUROPEAN SMART GRID RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FREE ACCESS TO EUROPE'S BEST SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

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- European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition
- Development of holistic, cyber-physical systems validation approach
- Enhancement of Hardware-in-the-Loop methodology and co-simulation tools
- Fostering of multi-lab testing procedures
- 20 partners from 13 European countries
- 21 first-class smart grid labs
- 8 virtual facilities and services
- Duration: 1 April 2020 - 30 September 2024

FREE PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL LAB ACCESS to leading smart grid and energy systems laboratories backed by concentrated know-how and best practices in:

- Power system components characterisation and evaluation
- Smart grid ICT/automation validation
- Co-simulation
- Real-time simulation and Power/ Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL)

and other topics.

Supported by the H2020 Programme under Contract No. 870620. The content of this display does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information expressed therein lies entirely with the ERIGRID consortium.

Appendix E: Presentation Template

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

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